

Framing the Problem: The Mystery of Post-Finasteride Syndrome and Reasons to Suspect a Microbial Factor

This post explains the features of Post-Finasteride Syndrome and tries to narrow down what is, and is not, probably causing it.

This blog is based on self-experimentation and research. It is not medical advice. Any information contained in this blog is for information purposes only. For medical advice or diagnosis, speak to a professional.

Executive Summary: Isolating the Third Factor

Post-Finasteride Syndrome (PFS) has symptoms and syndrome features which are hard to explain without a “third factor” (excluding genes/gene-expression as the first factor and external inputs such as drugs or supplements as the second).

Specifically:

- PFS includes symptoms that have no obvious link to hormones or androgen signalling.
- The syndrome features classic ‘recovery-to-crash’ cycles, i.e. rapid, cyclical fluctuations in symptoms.

The obviously androgenic symptoms of PFS could be attributable to faulty epigenetic signalling involving the androgen receptor (i.e. patients have enough hormones, but the hormones do not have the intended effect on the androgen receptor due to temporary gene silencing). However, androgenic symptoms fluctuate strongly, implying that something must be causing the epigenetics to fluctuate. Additionally, faulty androgen signalling struggles to explain the symptoms with no obvious link to androgens or hormones.

A third factor appears to be causing: 1) the non-androgenic symptoms, and 2) fluctuations in all symptoms. The presence of a microbe, or a community of microbes (dysbiosis), as this third factor might explain all these features¹.

Microbes could explain **non-androgenic symptoms** as well as **persistence, fluctuating symptoms, partial recoveries**, and other core features of PFS. By excreting large amounts of an enzyme known as **beta glucuronidase**, microbes can cause hormones intended for excretion to be reabsorbed in the gut. This could trigger epigenetic silencing as a compensation mechanism. Alternatively, microbes might directly trigger epigenetic silencing via another unknown mechanism. Microbes can emit compounds such as **hydrogen sulphide** or other by-products that could account for the non-androgenic symptoms of PFS.

¹ **Warning to PFS patients:** some antibiotics have been reported to worsen symptoms. Do not suddenly take antibiotics. In a future blog post I will describe the antibiotics that did/did not work for me with an accompanying hypothesis.

1. What is Post-Finasteride Syndrome

Post-Finasteride Syndrome (PFS) affects a subset of men who take Finasteride, a type of hormone blocker commonly used for treating male-pattern hair loss. We do not know what causes the condition. The condition can be life-altering and patient communities include frequent suicides.

Description of Core Symptoms

We know PFS causes an unusual constellation of sexual, physical, and cognitive side effects, listed in **Annex 1**. The symptoms in **Annex 1** are annotated as follows:

- (A)²: Clearly androgenic
- (B): Less clearly androgenic
- (C): No obvious androgenic link

Description of Core Features

These symptoms have a set of core features:

- **Persistence:** PFS typically begins with a ‘crash’ - a rapid onset of symptoms, sometimes overnight. After onset, PFS is very hard to eliminate. Some men have it for decades, seemingly permanently.
- **Recovery-to-crash cycles:** Some people recover and others do not. Some of those who recover stay well for a while before becoming ill again. Symptoms can return slowly over time, or suddenly, e.g. overnight. Symptoms can return without any obvious cause, or in response to a new intervention, such as a drug or supplement. Repeated cycles of recovery-crash-recovery are common, both in those who eventually recover fully, and those who do not.
- **No link between recoveries:** There is no obvious thread linking all recovery stories. People recover after interventions that span a large variety of medicines, supplements, dietary changes, or exercise, or a combination of these. Some people recover naturally over time. Some recoveries involve hormonal interventions, but many have no obvious hormonal angles. Recoveries are hard to repeat; what works for one person does not always work for others.
- **No diagnostic markers:** Standard blood tests often come back normal. So far, no consistent diagnostic marker indicates who has PFS. A study involving 16 patients detected altered neuro-steroids in cerebrospinal fluid and plasma³. High prolactin

² **Note:** (A) is defined as ‘clearly androgenic’ to mean a direct and first-order effect of a change in androgenic signalling. Non-PFS patients with androgen signalling problems may experience non-(A) symptoms, e.g. chronic fatigue. However, we do not know precisely why these patients have chronic fatigue, which may be a second-order effect in them as well as PFS patients. To avoid confusion, we will simply state that (A) is a direct and obvious knock-on of changes to androgen signalling in target tissues (e.g. muscle loss, sexual dysfunction, dry skin).

³ Melcangi et al.

levels are sometimes detected.

- **Overlapping but not identical symptoms:** Some core symptoms PFS are common to all or most sufferers, but there is a long ‘tail’ of heterogenous, low-frequency symptoms (e.g. eye damage, rapidly aging skin, prominent veins, lowered body temperature).
- **Partial link to androgen signalling:** Some core symptoms have obvious links to androgens (e.g. sexual dysfunction and dry skin) while others do not (e.g. chronic fatigue, suicidal ideation, impaired cognition, and anhedonia).
- **Subset of men:** PFS only affects a subset of men taking it.
- **Low dosage:** In some cases, PFS impacts men after just a single dose.

2. What We Know About Finasteride – and Why We Need a Wider Effect

Finasteride is a 5-alpha reductase inhibitor. 5-alpha reductase is an enzyme that converts testosterone into dihydrotestosterone, primarily in the prostate gland, skin (especially genital), liver, and hair follicles.

5-alpha reductase is also involved in the creation of bile acids and neuro-steroids. **Annex 2** contains a list of most of the known conversions of 5-alpha reductase, categorised.

It might seem logical to start looking for the cause for PFS in Annex 2: the precursors and outputs of 5-alpha reductase. However, we should consider the **broader picture first**.

A temporary breakdown in the production of any metabolite on the list in Annex 2 **does not** provide a good explanation for the core features of PFS (above), particularly persistence and recovery-to-crash cycles. No matter what the products of 5-alpha reductase do, all of them should theoretically restart after Finasteride is removed and 5-alpha reductase becomes active once more. If it were as simple as a lack of these products causing the syndrome, then removing Finasteride would resolve PFS.

Even a close match between a product of 5-alpha reductase and the core symptoms of PFS would **not explain** why the removal of Finasteride did not resolve the symptoms. Additionally, the products of 5-alpha reductase do not align closely with all core symptoms in any case.

Clearly, there is something missing in the explanation. We should consider what **sort of process** would explain the core symptoms of PFS, before investigating the products of 5-alpha reductase.

3. Search For a Process: Core Features of PFS

The core features of PFS are perhaps the hardest aspect of the condition to explain. Considering the list of core features of the symptoms, it seems reasonable to de-prioritise some explanations for the process that is causing PFS.

Less Likely Explanations – De-Prioritised

1. PFS is a simple adverse drug reaction to Finasteride

Reasons: If this were an adverse drug reaction, it would probably reverse when the drug is removed and would not be permanent. For symptoms to persist, the drug would have to cause lasting damage. Yet, Finasteride does not seem to cause obvious tissue damage and if it did, recovery should be impossible. An adverse drug reaction is also not consistent with other core features, including recovery-to-crash cycles.

2. PFS is imbalanced hormones

Reasons: Blood tests for hormones often come back normal. Furthermore, the endocrine system usually self-regulates and contains strong feedback mechanisms. It would be unusual for an imbalance in hormones to persist indefinitely, in a previously-health person, long after the medication was removed. This explanation also does not align with recovery-to-crash cycles. Additionally, while some sufferers benefit from exogenous hormones, others experience no benefit, while benefit from interventions that are only tangentially linked to hormones (e.g. supplements without a known hormonal effect, or dietary changes), suggesting hormones are not the sole cause.

3. PFS is permanent (unaltering) epigenetic changes

Reasons: Permanent epigenetic silencing struggles to account for recovery-to-crash cycles. This would imply rapid fluctuations in core symptoms while the underlying trigger that causes these symptoms (epigenetic silencing) remains unchanged. This is not easy to explain. Full recoveries are also hard to explain.

Partial Explanations – Retained but Incomplete

4. PFS is non-permanent (alterable) epigenetic changes

Reasons: Rapid alterations in gene expression match more closely what PFS patients experience through recovery-to-crash cycles. Interventions sometimes lead to a full remission of symptoms for a while. This often includes obvious androgen-signalling changes: a return of libido, erectile functioning, oil/sebum production on facial skin, and physical strength. It can also include the lifting of non-androgenic symptoms like cognitive and emotional fogs.

The clue that it involves androgen signalling is that the location of the changes in symptoms aligns with the locations with a high density of androgen receptors: the genital area, skeleton muscle, skin, and brain. These are also the areas where sufferers often feel first side effects from taking Finasteride (which blocks the formation of a hormone with high affinity for the androgen receptor).

A family doctor in the US has reported injecting PFS patients with high doses of testosterone, verified by blood test, and seeing no change in androgen signalling (e.g. no oily skin or acne), quote: *'they look like they are on an androgen blocker'*⁴. This testimony strongly suggests the hormone is not having the intended effect on its target despite sufficient hormone levels. In other words, the hormone is present in the body in sufficient quantities, as detected by blood test, but the androgen receptor, or perhaps another step farther in the androgen signalling process, appears turned off⁵.

The fluctuations in symptoms appear to be driven by the body's response to hormones, not the hormone level.

Temporary epigenetic changes provide a partial explanation but still does not account for the full spectrum of what PFS patients experience and report, as explained below.

⁴ William Powers, Dec 2025

⁵ Strictly speaking we do not know for certain that this is epigenetic silencing – perhaps it is an as-yet-unknown process. But we know that there is enough testosterone, yet it is not having the desired “effect on target” (i.e. the entire stream of androgen signalling steps). For the sake of argument, we will call it ‘non-permanent epigenetic silencing’ but there may be more to it.

5. Explanatory Gaps

Temporary epigenetic silencing is a good explanation for the androgenic symptoms of PFS, but it does not explain not-obviously androgenic core symptoms nor the fluctuations in all symptoms, both androgen and non-androgenic.

Explanatory Gap 1: Non-Androgenic Core Symptoms

Changes in androgen signalling can account for many of the symptoms in **Annex 1**, but not all of them. Of those which they do explain, it is hard to conceive of such an effect occurring without androgen signalling being involved due to very close alignment with the location of those effects and the known areas of high androgen receptor activity. As discussed previously we know there is enough hormone. Therefore, it seems quite clear that fault androgen signalling involved in PFS.

However, other symptoms are much less clearly associated with androgens. For example, chronic fatigue, tinnitus, anhedonia, rhabdomyolysis, and more. The categorisation of **Annex 1** into **(A) - obviously androgenic**, **(B) - less obviously androgenic**, and **(C) - no obvious androgenic link** helps display this visually.

This categorisation is not rigid and one can debate that some of (B) and (C) should be in (A). However, the point of it is not to classify each side effect precisely. The purpose is simply to show that androgen signalling is not a good explanation for all the core PFS symptoms and this should give us pause for thought, as it suggests a missing component in the aetiology.

Even with generous flexibility for (A), (B), and (C), it is hard to argue that androgenic silencing provides a **logical** and **neat explanation** for all the core symptoms of PFS.

Explanatory Gap 2: Trigger for Symptom Fluctuations

For many patients, all PFS symptoms fluctuate in the recovery-crash cycle. This includes **all the symptoms - everything can fluctuate** - both those that are clearly androgenic (A), as well as the non-androgenic symptoms (B) and (C).

A recovery can include the lifting of many or all symptoms. Symptoms can fluctuate independently, with some worsening while others improve. Non-androgenic symptoms, in particular, can move independently of each other and independently of the androgenic symptoms. Interestingly, androgenic symptoms tend to move as a block: when libido and erectile function improve, it is usually the case that genital shrinkage and other androgen symptoms improve too.

Something is causing all symptoms to fluctuate, even if they are not necessarily all moving in the same direction at the same time.

6. Sub-Analysis of the Fluctuations in Symptoms

Here we discuss symptom fluctuation to ensure clarity.

- **Non-androgenic symptoms:** We do not know why non-androgenic symptoms fluctuate, but the obvious answer is that whatever is causing the symptoms in the first place is also causing them to fluctuate by being present in one moment, and not in the next. The symptom trigger is presumably ebbing and flowing, and this causes the symptoms to come and go. This is the simplest answer and is also complete in that it has no obvious gaps.
- **Androgenic symptoms:** As discussed, these symptoms appear to be linked to androgen receptor expression. If this is fluctuating, it means that something is causing the body to turn its epigenome off and on again, repeatedly.

It is highly unlikely that the body is silencing/un-silencing its androgen receptors for **no reason whatsoever**. It is much more logical that a factor is causing epigenetic fluctuations.

We might suppose this is a completely independent ‘fourth factor’ but this becomes excessively complex for no good reason: the shortest and most logical answer is that trigger causing non-androgenic symptoms is the same as, or linked to, the androgen receptor silencing - otherwise we have to suppose PFS is composed of two completely unrelated problems and the explanation for the aetiology of PFS begins to become bizarre.

The shortlist of culprits that can change androgen signalling is limited. As far as we know, it can only involve:

- Your body (your DNA and the expression of those genes).
- Whatever you put into your body (drugs, hormones, other compounds), or perhaps an external factor like radiation.
- Your microbiome.

Less likely explanations for androgenic symptom fluctuation

1. Your body

Reasons: This would mean that your own body is creating strong fluctuations in its own *baseline* gene expression (namely, one day your body responds strongly to its own testosterone, and then next day it does not) without anything to trigger it. It would mean the body is **continually self-disrupting its androgen receptors**, and that it starts doing this only after taking a drug, sometimes a single dose, and **continues indefinitely** (no continuous external triggers).

‘Your body’ is just DNA and the epigenetic mechanisms that expose or hide that DNA from transcription. If the body is the sole cause of these symptom fluctuations, one of two things must be happening: 1) the DNA itself is mutating/changing, which is highly improbable, or 2) the epigenetics are fluctuating autonomously. This means the histones spooling your DNA are continually opening and closing, turning androgen signalling on and off. This would require an internal signal constantly commanding the body to turn on and off its own

receptors. Even if this unknown mechanism were found it still would struggle to explain the non-androgenic symptoms.

Furthermore, PFS patients experience remissions after supplements or drugs. This would imply that sometimes the body turns its androgen receptors on and off entirely on its own, and other times only in response to a supplement, creating two separate accounts for the silencing/unsilencing that need explanations.

2. Whatever you put into your body, or external factors

Reasons: Patients often take a medicine or supplement and find themselves at a new, better baseline that continues for an extended period, **much longer than it takes the medicine or supplement to be excreted** from the body. This better baseline can extend for months, or in some cases years. Sometimes the symptoms slowly fade back in. In other cases, a disruption such as a new supplement or medicine causes symptoms to return suddenly. The return can sometimes make the baseline worse than it was before.

The key fact is that the **baseline can be 'sticky'**, remaining in place long after a medicine or supplement leaves the body. This is not consistent with the thing being put into the body maintaining the new baseline. If the new baseline stays when the thing has gone, something else is causing the change to stay.

3. Why it might be your microbiome

Explained below.

Visualisation of Why a Third Factor Provides a Neat Explanation for Post-Finasteride Syndrome

7. Microbes Can Explain Core PFS Features and Symptoms

Microbes might be this “third factor”⁶.

The microbiome, particularly in the gut, operates partially independently of your body and anything you put in it or expose it to. The microbiome is involved in the metabolism of hormones, so can plausibly create androgenic side-effects. Microbes can create their own symptoms that are not linked to androgens.

Previous research has shown changes in gut microbiota in PFS patients⁷. Hence, we know the microbiome of PFS patients is different. However, a microbial shift might be **the primary mechanism** that accounts for the missing non-androgen symptoms of PFS and its core features including **persistence**, the **recovery-to-crash** cycles with ‘sticky’ baselines, the **inconsistent recoveries** stories, and others.

“Locking” Symptoms into Place Via Dysbiosis

If the presence of Finasteride altered the microbial community, this new community would “lock” into place, creating a new equilibrium that remains after the removal of the drug. Once a dysbiosis community was well-established in the gut, it would persist. Dysbiotic communities, like many infections, change their environment to protect themselves.

Microbial communities can **emit a host of by-products** that could account for **non-androgenic symptoms (B)**, and **(C)**.

A microbial community could perpetually **disrupt hormone metabolism** and cause epigenetic side effects, for example by **recirculating the hormones** the body attempts to excrete back into the body via the gut. This process could render the body unable to eliminate hormones normally and trigger epigenetic silencing as a compensation mechanism.

Once this new microbial community gains a competitive advantage it would be difficult, but not impossible, to remove them. This would explain the strange windows of recovery followed by crashes and the variety of interventions that result in remissions.

⁶ This theory was first proposed by Mitchison, E.C. 2026

⁷ Borgo et al.

TL;DR - The Hypothesis

A HYPOTHESIZED LINK BETWEEN POST-FINASTERIDE SYNDROME (PFS) AND GUT DYSBIOSIS

Androgenic Symptoms

Dysbiosis produces beta-glucuronidase, or an unknown compound, which 'locks' the epigenetic silencing of androgen signalling – creating (A) symptoms:

- Loss of libido
- Erectile dysfunction
- Impotence
- Penile and testicular shrinkage

And the other PFS symptoms obviously governed by the androgen receptor or its downstream signalling.

Non-Androgenic Symptoms

Dysbiosis produces waste products like hydrogen sulphide, hydrogen, methane, lipopolysaccharides (LPS), peptoglycans, ammonia, and others – creating (B) and (C) symptoms:

- Chronic fatigue
- Muscle loss
- Slowed cognition and memory
- Depression
- Anhedonia

And many other not-obviously-androgenic PFS symptoms.

This is a hypothesized model; consult with a medical professional.

Filling Explanatory Gap 1 – Non-Androgen Core Symptoms

- These are directly caused by the microbes, for example through by-products such as **hydrogen sulphide gas**.

Microbes can generate waste products, particularly hydrogen sulphide gas, hydrogen, methane, lipopolysaccharides (LPS), peptoglycans, ammonia, d-lactic acid, ethanol & acetaldehyde, indoles, skatoles, and deconjugated bile acids. The list of side effects that these compounds could produce is much larger and covers a wide range of PFS symptoms, potentially covering all remaining symptoms.

Hydrogen sulphide, in particular, can act as a mitochondrial poison in large quantities, causing chronic fatigue, depression, anhedonia, muscle wastage, strong cognitive impairment, memory loss, and other unpleasant side effects. It acts like **cyanide**, blocking an enzyme called cytochrome c oxidase in the mitochondrial electron transport chain. This blocks aerobic respiration for the cell.

Filling Explanatory Gap 2 – Trigger for Symptom Fluctuation

Non-androgenic symptoms (B) and (C):

- The fluctuations are simply due to fluctuations in the ‘toxins’ produced by the microbes (above). When they produce more by-products, symptoms worsen. When they produce less, symptoms lessen.

Androgenic symptoms (A):

- For the androgen signalling symptoms, there are at least two potential ways microbes could be causing shifts in epigenetic androgen gene expression (i.e. altering the “effect on target” of testosterone, dihydrotestosterone, oestrogen and perhaps others)

Microbial epigenetic silencing mechanism theory 1

Beta glucuronidase and enterohepatic recirculation

When the liver attempts to excrete hormones it attached glucuronic acid to it, through a process called glucuronidation. This ‘tags’ the hormone, rendering it possible for the body to excrete into the bile and the digestive tract.

Some microbes in the gut possess an enzyme called beta-glucuronidase that removes these chemical ‘tags’ to consume the glucuronic acid, a sugar acid. This feeds the microbe but liberates the hormone. The hormone can then be re-absorbed through the gut wall, in a process called enterohepatic recirculation (literally, ‘gut-liver recirculation’).

Theoretically, if too much ‘untagging’ happened because of large amounts of beta glucuronidase, the hormones would circulate endlessly. In other words, the body would be unable to eliminate the hormone. The inability to excrete oestrogen, testosterone, or other hormones despite attempting to do repeatedly, might trigger the body to turn off its androgen receptors to compensate. This could create the **core ‘androgenic’ PFS symptoms** –

androgen receptors are turned off because the body is **unable to lower its hormones naturally**.

Fluctuations in the output of this microbial community could cause fluctuations in the levels of circulating androgens or other hormones like oestrogen. This could cause fluctuations in epigenetic signalling. This could explain the fluctuations in symptoms that PFS patients experience.

Microbial epigenetic silencing theory 2:

Direct epigenetic silencing

A second way microbes could cause PFS is a theoretical as-yet-unknown direct silencing process. Perhaps, instead of creating epigenetic silencing through hormonal ‘waste accumulation’ through impaired glucuronidation, a compound produced by the gut microbes might directly trigger epigenetic silencing all on its own. This compound might be hydrogen sulphide gas. For reasons unknown, this compound hits the androgen receptors first. Hypothetically, the body may consider the androgen receptors to be less essential and therefore turns them off in response to this stressor. So, instead of triggering epigenetic silencing by causing an accumulation of hormones, the microbes emit something else that simply turns off the androgen receptor on its own.

Explanations for Core Features of PFS Supposing a Microbial Factor

Reassessing the core features of PFS and considering how microbes might fit in:

Feature	Explanation with Microbes
Persistence	PFS symptoms persist, despite removal of the drug, because the dysbiosis remains. The new community are entrenched in the gut, stubbornly resisting removal.
Recovery-to-crash cycles	Temporary changes to the composition of the microbial community (or the enzymes or by-products it is emitting) causes symptoms to briefly lift, creating a window of feeling ‘cured’, before eventually the microbes’ defence mechanisms kick in and symptoms return. Microbial communities are difficult to eradicate, and may alter the environment in the small intestine to its favour, preventing its complete eradication. Worsening of the symptoms after an intervention is caused by more ‘bad microbes’ or ‘bad by-products’.
Lack of obvious links in recoveries	A microbial community would respond to multiple types of treatment: medicines, supplements, dietary shifts, and exercise. Differences in the microbial communities between individuals could cause some differences in responses to treatments. Mixed responses to antibiotics are because only some of them are effective against the relevant microbe(s).

Lack of consistent diagnostic markers	N/A - This can be explained by epigenetic silencing; does not specifically require microbes.
Overlapping but not identical symptoms	Differences in the precise composition of the microbes could cause them to create different by-products, or create the same by-products in different quantities, causing a spectrum of symptoms and severity. Individuals could also have differing sensitivities to the by-products.
Partial link to androgen signalling	Androgen symptoms are caused by the microbes interfering with the normal hormone cycle, or because they're emitting an unknown epigenetic-silencing compound. Non-androgen symptoms are caused by compounds the microbes produce ⁸ .
Subset of men	Only men with an underlying microbiome predisposed to dysbiosis, or with an epigenome vulnerable to the theoretical silencing 'compound' produced by the bacteria, would be susceptible.
Low dosage	Some men's microbiomes might be close enough to dysbiosis that a single dose could trigger it.

Conclusion

Microbes theoretically fill many explanatory gaps in the aetiology of PFS. If this theory is correct, it implies that there could be a **microbial treatment** that would eliminate or at least partially reduce PFS symptoms. It should be possible to **test for the presence of these microbes and their enzymes**. In a subsequent post, I will outline the treatments that have helped and those that have not, and a rationale for why.

I will publish this paper on a scientific pre-print server so it is time-stamped.

Thank you for reading.

Avery X. Trace, Scotland, April 2026

⁸ Note: a microbial factor could also explain why the symptoms PFS patients get before the crash (i.e. while on Finasteride) are not always the same as those they get after they develop PFS. While on Finasteride, they are mainly experiencing the androgen signalling issues, whereas after the removal of Finasteride they also have symptoms directly created by the dysbiotic microbes.

Annex 1 – Core Symptoms of PFS

This is a non-exhaustive list⁹. It describes the most commonly-reported symptoms. Others may have had symptoms not reported here.

(A): Clearly androgenic

(B): Less clearly androgenic

(C): No obvious androgenic link

Sexual

- **Libido** - Decreased or complete loss of sex drive. **(A)**
- **Erectile** - Erectile dysfunction, impotence, loss of morning, and spontaneous erections. **(A)**
- **Orgasm disorders** - Sexual anhedonia, loss of pleasurable orgasm. **(A)**
- **Ejaculatory disorders** - Decreased semen volume and force. **(A)**
- **Penis** - Penile shrinkage and numbness. Peyronie's disease. **(A)**
- **Testes** - Scrotal shrinkage and numbness. **(A)**

Physical

- **Gynecomastia** - Female-like breast development and enlargement. **(A)**
- **Fatigue** - Chronic fatigue. Listlessness. **(B)**
- **Muscle** – Muscle loss. **(A)** Myalgia, including muscle pain. **(C)** Myopathy, including muscle weakness cramps, stiffness and tetany (twitching). **(C)** Myasthenia, including muscle weakness. **(B)** Rhabdomyolysis, including muscle atrophy. **(C)** Creatine kinase elevation. **(B)**
- **Skin** - Decreased oil and sebum production. **(A)** Chronically dry, thinning of skin. **(A)** Melasma (brownish macules and patches that typically affect sun-exposed areas on the face). **(B)**
- **Tissue** - Lipoatrophy (localized loss of fat tissue). **(B)**
- **Hearing** - Tinnitus (ringing in the ears). **(C)**
- **Vision** - Optic neuropathy (damage inflicted on the optic nerve). Retinopathy (disease of the retina). Ocular toxicity (includes inflammation and atrophy of the optic nerve and inner retina, loss of white matter, and gliosis of the occipital and parietal lobes causing various degrees of blindness). **(C)**
- **Metabolism** - Diabetes mellitus. **(C)** Increased fat deposition, obesity and elevated body mass index. **(A)** Decrease in body temperature. **(A)** Reduced HDL cholesterol, raised fasting glucose and triglycerides. **(B)** Elevated rheumatoid factor. **(B)**
- **Self-Harm** - Attempted suicide. Completed suicide. **(C)**

Mental & Neurological

- **Memory** - Severe memory/recall impairment. **(B)**
- **Cognition** - Slowed thought processes. Impaired problem solving, decreased comprehension. **(B)**
- **Psychological** - Depression. **(C)** Anxiety. **(C)** Suicidal ideation. **(C)**

⁹ Helpfully provided by The Post-Finasteride Syndrome Foundation - thank you:
<https://www.pfsfoundation.org/about-pfs-post-finasteride-syndrome/>

- **Emotional** - Emotional flatness and anhedonia. (C)
- **Sleep** - Insomnia. (B) Obstructive sleep apnea. (B)
- **Self-Harm** - Suicidal ideation. (C)

Annex 2 - What 5-Alpha Reductase Does

Most known conversions of substrate **to** product.

Androgens

- Testosterone **to** 5 α -Dihydrotestosterone (DHT)
- Androstenedione **to** 5 α -Androstanedione
- Epitestosterone **to** 5 α -Dihydroepitestosterone

Progestogens & Neurosteroids

- Progesterone **to** 5 α -Dihydroprogesterone (5 α -DHP)
- 3 α -Dihydroprogesterone **to** Allopregnanolone
- 3 β -Dihydroprogesterone **to** Isopregnanolone

Corticosteroids

- Deoxycorticosterone (DOC) **to** 5 α -Dihydrodeoxycorticosterone (5 α -DHDOC)
- Corticosterone **to** 5 α -Dihydrocorticosterone
- Cortisol **to** 5 α -Dihydrocortisol
- Aldosterone **to** 5 α -Dihydroaldosterone

Bile Acid Intermediates

- Cholestenone **to** 5 α -Cholestanone
- 7 α -hydroxy-4-cholesten-3-one **to** 7 α -hydroxy-5 α -cholestan-3-one

Anabolic

- Nandrolone **to** 5 α -Dihydroneandrolone (5 α -DHN)

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